

COMPUTER SCIENCES

PARADIGMS OF APPLICATION OF ERP SYSTEMS AND BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE IN BUSINESS

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Abstract

The purpose of this research paper is to systematically analyze and consider, based on a successive search of relevant literature, the main effects of digital business transformation through projects introducing ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) systems and applying sophisticated business intelligence technologies. The basic characteristic of modern business is that today companies and business systems have access to huge amounts of data, but unfortunately only 5 to 10% of all that data is used for business purposes. Recent research, supported by practical results, shows that digital business transformation, i.e. the implementation of ERP systems as well as software, methods, techniques and tools based on business intelligence (BI), greatly helps companies gain a competitive advantage. The results of the research show that in the process of applying ERP systems and business intelligence, a good knowledge and understanding of the functionality of business processes is important and crucial, precisely a complete understanding of business processes is possible by conducting a business analysis and obtaining the information needed for the implementation of business intelligence processes in companies. Representative research indicates that in the process of implementing ERP systems and business intelligence, good knowledge and understanding of the functionality of a company's business processes are important and crucial, followed by support from top management, clear goals and vision, selection of adequate software solutions, upgrade options, etc. Current research indicates that although there is a certain number of scientific works, that is, research in this area, there are still doubts in the process of introduction, that is, in the project management segment of the ERP system and business intelligence, about the process methodology of the introduction itself. The research results show that in this sense it is particularly important that business systems and organizations are able to correctly set up data in everyday business operations and that this business data significantly assists them in the business decision-making process. Starting from the aforementioned research problems and based on the insufficient number of conducted empirical research at the global level, the device raises the question of how the application of the concept of ERP system project management and business intelligence contributes to the efficiency of business process management.

Keywords: ERP sistem, artificial intelligence, business intelligence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Some authors state that part of the changes related to the application of information-communication technologies in business are related to the phenomenon of globalization, which, according to some authors, has initiated teamwork in real conditions in business systems, where it is created on the basis of teamwork, with the involvement of all employees in their organizations, in the execution of tasks and work tasks (Mockaitis, Zander, & De Cieri, 2018). Positive changes depend on the

vision and strategy of the company, i.e. the quality of the decision-making process, where the so-called "good decisions" must in principle be based on the knowledge and experience of direct managers and which are crucial for the decision-making process and require accurate, timely and reliable information (Denić N., 2016). According to the results of research by some authors Kielstra, the most important attributes of information needed for decision-making are: quality (65%), com-

pleteness (18%), timeliness (13%), and price (5%). Research indicates that the introduction of a business intelligence system is one of the riskiest information technology investments, which, due to its complexity, requires cooperation between the IT sector and business management, accounting and finance staff, and company managers at the operational level in order to create business value (Wagner & Weitzel, 2012). As many as 54% of business users cannot find the information they need, 43% are not sure whether the information they receive is accurate, while 77% claim that bad decisions are made solely due to a lack of information. In the latest representative literature, some eminent authors emphasize that business intelligence strives to make creative people want to be even more creative, that is, to strive for success and consider it the most important value in their lives, and creativity is the key to knowledge necessary for achieving success (Deuze, 2018), while the use of ERP systems in business systems is a response to the demands for faster and more efficient business operations. In the literature, it is emphasized that the ERP system should essentially be software that, through the application of information technology, unifies all business processes of the company. (Madininos, Chatzoudes, & Tsairidis, 2012)

2. SPECIFICITIES OF MANAGEMENT OF ERP SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION PROJECTS

In the latest representative literature, it is pointed out that the process of introducing software projects often faces certain problems such as resistance to changes, resistance of end users in adapting to new technology, inadequate requirements and lack of management support (Salim, Suleiman & Salisu, 2015), also some authors emphasize that in the introduction of a new ERP system, the business system must also take into account certain key success factors (Ngai et al., 2008). ERP systems are built to provide a centralized and comprehensive view of an organization's data. In the literature, it is stated that ERP, i.e. enterprise resource planning systems, represent a complete, integrated platform that manages all aspects of enterprise operations such as production, distribution, accounting and finance, controlling, human resources, and others (Stojanović et al., 2024). However, managing ERP system implementation projects can be a very complicated activity and requires strong managerial leadership and project management because the project must often be evaluated (Motiwalla & Thompson, 2012). In many recent studies, it can be clearly seen that many companies that have introduced ERP systems have not upgraded or fully utilized this system to create business success (Zhu et al., 2010). Numerous ERP systems are available in Serbia, from global solutions such as SAP S/4HANA, Microsoft Dynamics 365, Oracle NetSuite, to flexible options such as Odoo, which are increasingly used in small and medium-sized enterprises (Denić N., 2024). Botta - Genoulaz and Millet (2006) indicate that apart from ERP being focused on the enterprise and resources, it goes beyond the planning function and also includes other tasks such as financial control, operations management, analysis and reporting, and routine decision support. Practice shows that ERP systems provide transparency in the entire

business process by monitoring all aspects of production, logistics and finance (Denić N., 2023). Modern ERP systems often include real-time analytics, cloud deployment, and mobile access to enable seamless collaboration and decision-making across teams. We will summarize the trends expected in the ERP information services market according to an article by one of the largest suppliers of ERP services, Oracle NetSuite (Jenkins, 2025): cloud ERP service, two-tier ERP services - level 2, digital transformation, integration of other technologies with ERP systems, personalization, artificial intelligence, predictive analytics and mobile ERP application. The choice of ERP system depends on the size and specific needs of the business, with different options available to support different processes, such as finance, sales, inventory management and human resources. In recent literature reviews, scholars have identified critical success factors (CSFs), which have mostly been investigated from a generic perspective (Lech, 2016; Saade & Nijher, 2016). In his article, Rocket (2022) lists 4 main sources for the formation of KFU, namely: KFU specific to the industry; Strategy, Industry Position and Geographic Location and Environmental Factors. Theory and examples in practice unequivocally indicate that despite the existing literature on ERP systems, there is a noticeable lack of research on the success of project management of the introduction of business intelligence and ERP systems from the user's perspective, that is, there is an extremely limited number of researches available considering the user's perception of the ERP system implementation process (Vujović, V., 2020). What is emphasized in the latest research is that people dealing with business intelligence must be creative, look for new solutions (original), think and often look for how to adapt the system to different situations (flexible) (Kennett et al., 2018), have the ability to express in words (Dwight et al., 2018) and be especially creative thinking (Mastria et al., 2018).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, we use several research methods, so that we can get a complete approach to solving the selected problems. In the introductory theoretical part, the descriptive method was used, with which we introduced ourselves and presented the basic concepts in the field of ERP systems and business intelligence - their functionality, suppliers, trending methods and implementation strategies. This part contains a detailed comprehensive theory - an analytical review of the reference scientific literature and scientific works of well-known foreign experts of recent date. Given the research topic and issues, and the particularly pronounced multidisciplinary character of the research, a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods was used for the purposes of the research (Radovanovic, 2020).

4. RESULTS

ERP systems can be tailored to businesses of all sizes and industries, offering flexibility, scalability and efficiency. In earlier research, a high percentage of ERP implementation failures was recorded, and other researchers often referred to the results of these studies,

which emphasized the risk in the implementation project. Well-known authors estimate that up to 70% of failures are in the establishment of ERP systems (Iskanius, 2010). In this sense, it is said that in companies according to Davenport et.al. (2007), 47% of respondents adapted their ERP systems. This is supported by research conducted by the Gartner group, including 1,300 companies, of various types of activity and structure, where it was determined that 32 ERP system projects exceeded the installation time. However, despite the fact that the latest research in the world indicates that, for example, out of 43 American companies that participated in the research, 46% achieved 100% or less return on investment, 34% between 101% and 1000%, and 20% around 1001% and more, they are still not applied in SMEs in Serbia to the necessary and sufficient extent. Similarly, the Standish Group Report indicates that the implementation took 2.5 times longer than the companies expected, which caused the lack of expected effects. Research regarding the return on investment period indicates the following situation: 49% of companies recovered their invested BIS funds in one year or less, 32% in the period from one to three years, 19% in three or more years. Research results in the world indicate that a typical business intelligence project has an average return of over 430%, however, despite this, companies in Serbia decide to purchase new equipment and software to follow fashion trends and thus impress their business partners, rather than truly believing that new IT, both in terms of hardware and software, can make their work easier, which is especially pronounced

in socially owned companies. A study by Meta Group, in which 200 companies participated, revealed that the implementation of an ERP system will cost an average of about 1% of corporate costs, and that 70% of that will go to paying for human resources. The following is an example of Nestle's Globe project, which was designed to standardize supply chain processes and involved more than 230,000 employees, cost more than 2.4 billion dollars. Meta Group, however, estimates that the average project duration is about 20 months. In a research study involving 66 companies, Soja found that 50% of projects lasted less than a year. Deloitte (1999) found in a study involving 66 companies, of various types of activities and business programs, randomly selected from 500, that the average length of ERP system implementation is up to four years. As business strategies and markets change, ERP systems must be adapted to these new, changed conditions. The research "KMPG's Business intelligence Survey" attempted to answer certain key questions related to business intelligence systems and their use. The results of this research show that; 19% of managers make their decisions on the basis of intuition, i.e., they base more than 50% of their decisions on intuition. The next 19% of managers, 30% to 50% of decisions also make decisions without the support of information. Less than 10% of managers base their decisions largely on data from a business intelligence system. The number of decisions made by managers based on data is shown in the following figure (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. How many decisions made by managers are based on data?

Source: (KPMG, 2019)

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Many well-known authors in their research emphasize that a successfully introduced ERP system brings many strategic, organizational, management and technological advantages (Zhu, Li, Wang & Chen 2010), but also disadvantages that are mainly of a technical and business nature. The purpose of ERP software is to help organizations improve productivity, make data-driven decisions, improve collaboration, and achieve better overall efficiency. Existing recent literature and research by well-known experts on unsuccessful ERP system implementation projects in most countries of the world simply explains the failure in terms of lack of resources of sufficient skills, lack of technology, lack of money, user resistance and other cultural issues (Bitsini, 2015). Practice shows that achieving benefits from an ERP investment is not the same for all companies. Some companies immediately saw the benefits they expected, but unfortunately for the majority of companies this was not the case. In a good part of the literature, you can find the results of the research on the effects of the implementation of the ERP system, which

show that on average approximately 53% of the companies achieved less than 50% of the benefits they expected from the implementation of these projects. In the implementation of a new ERP system, it is evident that there are errors and problems, in this regard, many researchers believe that identifying and adhering to CSFs will reduce or eliminate problems and increase the likelihood of successful preparation and implementation of an information solution (Ram & Corkindale, 2013). Some authors state that lack of management support, insufficient support and involvement of management can negatively affect the success of ERP implementation (Rajapakse and Thushara, 2023). Lack of adequate employee training can lead to resistance and inefficient use of the system (Rajapakse and Thushara, 2023). A well-known author states that during the ERP system implementation process it is necessary to have: support from top management, a clear vision and measurable goals, quality of business data, selection of an adequate ERP solution, continuous improvements, etc. (DeBriere, 2024). A business example from the practice of the company "Obilić Petrol" shows that when people

buy a sandwich, 72% also buy coffee, but this percentage drops rapidly in June, July, August and September and is only 23%, i.e. sandwich sales are still the same, but they do not take coffee with it. The managers of the company "Obilić Petrol" realized that during those months when the temperatures were significantly higher, customers would rather have something refreshing than buy coffee. They decided to make the

right move and, in addition to coffee, introduced the sale of lemonade into regular sales during those four months. Customers responded favorably to this and now, in those four months, lemonade sales have compensated for the losses from unsold coffee..

Fig. 2. Selling sandwiches, coffee and lemonade
Source: author's research.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The result and scientific contribution of this research will be reflected, among other things, in the qualitative and quantitative analysis of relevant literature and the current practice of introducing business intelligence systems and ERP systems in the function of improving business, in particular, leading to more efficient business decision-making through efficient data management and more precise event prediction. Today, business managers have at their disposal appropriate tools based on intelligent systems, artificial technology - neural networks, expert systems, genetic algorithms, phase systems and others, which help management and decision-making bodies of companies in complex business processes. Today, small and medium-sized enterprises can benefit from the accessibility and modularity of solutions such as Odoo, Zoho or Acumatica, while large corporations may prefer the depth and complexity of platforms such as Oracle NetSuite, SAP S/4HANA, or Microsoft Dynamics 365. Nevertheless, due to its versatility and price, Odoo remains one of the most interesting open source ERP solutions on the market, and due to its adaptability, it is suitable for small, medium-sized and larger companies (Emley, 2024). ERP tools for small businesses are usually located in the Cloud and are quickly installed, in this sense, today the obvious choice for implementing ERP in the Cloud because this solution reduces initial costs, is easy to customize, updates automatically, allows you to access your ERP from anywhere and anytime (Denić N., 2014). The Standish Group report on ERP implementation projects, which states that these projects exceeded the planned project budgets by approximately 178%, lasted 2.5 times longer and provided only 30% of the promised profit or planned profit. The latest research shows that 40% of major decisions are not made based on facts, but on the manager's feelings. Based on a review of the relevant literature, the strengths can be mainly divided into operational, managerial, strategic, technical and organizational, while the weaknesses are mainly business and technical. The largest regional

player is the Novi Sad company M&I Systems. Followed by AB Soft, ASW inženjering and Europos. UPIS ERP of the Serbian company IIB also works in Serbia, the region and several African countries. We believe that the thesis offers practical insights into the challenges and good practices of ERP implementation, which can be helpful to all companies that are embarking on the path of digital business transformation. The success of the implementation of the solution is not guaranteed. In the literature, it is stated that in 2024, 72% of companies had problems with the digital transformation process. As the ERP market continues to evolve in 2025, cloud solutions remain the dominant trend, offering scalability, real-time insight and lower infrastructure costs. In this sense, the most common problem they cite is lack of knowledge or appropriate personnel (52%), followed by lack of financial resources with 43%, and with 37%, the reason companies identified was that their business could not adapt to changes in the environment. However, research in practice shows that half of companies and business systems still believe that digital transformation is not necessary for successful business. Statistics also showed that ERP is used by 29% of companies, of which 29% are small, 59% are medium and 82% are large companies. The key to a successful ERP implementation lies in understanding the specific needs of your organization and choosing a platform that aligns with your long-term goals.

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